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PDE6B in resistance and progression in cancer.

Shahan K. Mamoor, B.S., M.S., Ph.D cand.¹
¹shahanmamoor@gmail.com
Chestnut Hill, MA USA 02467
East Islip, NY USA 11730

Phosphodiesterases are attractive therapeutic targets in cancer because in general their function is less likely to be required for cellular viability in normal cells as compared to other genes tumors produce in high quantity. Their requirement for cellular viability together with their differential expression based on quantitative determination of therapeutic index suggests their potential importance as adjunctive therapeutics. We identified the phosphodiesterase enzyme PDE6B as a therapeutic vulnerability in resistance and progression in cellular systems that model resistance in human cancer. Systems biologic study indicated likely mechanisms of actions associated with PDE6B function in cancer including expression of solute carrier channel family genes SLC25A4 and SLC25A5 as well as co-regulation with cell death program genes BAD and BAX.